

COMPOSITES - THE WAY AHEAD

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ABSTRACT

Since the invention of carbon fibre composites at the Royal Aircraft Establishment at Farnborough in 1964, major steps have been made in its understanding as a composite material and the methods of application to produce aircraft structures. However, neither the material nor these applications have been truly optimised and many actions need to be taken to achieve this goal.

Each area, from the fibre to the ultimate application of the composite material, has been identified and the current status defined. From this datum, consideration has been given to action necessary to increase the ability to apply composites to aircraft structures. The aspects covered are material properties, design consideration, manufacturing methods and cost reduction. For each element, the way ahead has been defined.

In conclusion, despite the emergence of improved metallics and the potential application of Metallic Matrix Composites, the future application of composites is assured if the appropriate developments are effected.

INTRODUCTION

Fibre reinforced composites have attained a level of application in military aircraft rivalling that held by the more conventional aluminium alloys. However, the battle, if it can be so called, is not won due to a number of reasons including the improvements being effected and planned for the competing materials.

Why has this battle not been fought with similar enthusiasm in the civil field? The first fully compositised aircraft failed to reach the market place.

Whilst composites have a firm foothold in the aircraft industry their application has not been without difficulty and the problems of increasing their application and performance is a challenge that is being grasped with enthusiasm worldwide.

In order to understand the way ahead perhaps it is necessary to pause and consider the activities and developments that have led to the current levels of application. In addition, the reasons for the application of composites and both potential and necessary developments require consideration.

LOOKING BACK

Did the Wright Brothers realise in 1903 the industry that they had laid the foundation stones for? From their delicate machines blossomed the world's aviation industry which, during the 1960's, relied almost entirely on aluminium alloys for fabrication of their structure. Apart from minor alloy developments and improvements in design techniques and processing methods it began to appear that this was the material for all time and that stagnation had set in. However, as it is now clear, this was far from the truth.

Carbon fibre materials have been in existence for many years but it is only in the past two decades that fibres exhibiting sufficiently high strength and stiffness have been developed to make them competitive with the more conventional materials. The birth of these efficient fibres occurred during 1964 at the Royal Aircraft Establishment, Farnborough. Now, in 1987, some 23 years further on, compositisation of a typical military aircraft has reached 25% and of a civil aircraft 10%. Realistically, it can be anticipated that 60% of the structure could be compositised. If this is the level of compositisation, will it take 55 years and 230 years to reach on military and civil aircraft respectively?

I believe that the answer is NO! Successful application brings confidence, bringing further applications, stimulating development by the material suppliers, design organisations, manufacturing areas and the machine tool industry by developing equipment to aid in the reduction of manufacturing costs.

Let us now consider the developments that are taking place in the areas that are essential to the continued growth in the application of composites.

COMPOSITE MATERIALS

Composite strength is a function, primarily of the fibre, but in many modes the ability of the matrix to support these fibres is of paramount importance. Clearly, in order to achieve optimum properties, improvements in both constituents must be achieved in addition to the all important field of fibre-resin interface properties.

Consider the fibre. All strength, with the exception of those depending on interlaminar properties, are almost directly proportional to the basic fibre strength. Laminate stiffness is also proportional to the basic fibre stiffness. Clearly then, optimisation of fibre strength and stiffness is a fundamental objective for all fibre manufacturers. Figure 1 shows the improvements that have been achieved in fibre properties with time and indicates the direction, at least from the military aspect, in which developments should be directed.

Figure 1. Improvements in fibre properties

It is well known that improvements in fibre strength can be obtained at the expense of stiffness and vice versa and it is essential that the fabricators identify to the suppliers the compromise that best satisfies their individual requirements. This in itself can be a daunting task as structures which may historically have been strength designed can, due to aeroelastic or flutter requirements, become stiffness dominated. Compromise is therefore necessary to ensure that the best balance of properties is obtained from the project material or that different materials are used in different components. This latter approach can increase material procurement costs and does increase the cost of manufacture.

An assessment has been made of the mass sensitivity of a modern high performance military wing to changes in strength and stiffness of the fibres; it is assumed that these properties are fully translated into those of the laminate. With the minimisation of mass as one of the major design goals it can be seen from Figure 2 that mass savings can be effected by increasing both strength and stiffness with stiffness being the strongest driver.

Figure 2. Mass sensitivity of a military aircraft wing to changes in fibre strength and stiffness

The brittleness of the first generation composites led to the materials exhibiting poor tolerance to low energy impact and a susceptibility to damage during manufacture and service life. This brittleness of the laminate can be laid directly at the door of the matrix and whilst significant improvements have been made to matrix properties, this is the archilles heel of thermoset composite systems.

Many methods are available for the assessment of brittleness (or toughness) but that considered most relevant to the structural engineer is the measurement of residual strength after subjecting the laminate to impact by a low energy projectile. This being representative of runway debris or misuse during manufacture or service life.

An attempt has been made to show the improvements that have been obtained in compression after impact with time and this is shown on Figure 3. The objective with this property is to equal or exceed other compression properties which are also being driven higher by material developments.

Figure 3. Improvements in compression properties with time

In the world of composites, thermoset materials have been dominant but recently solvent resistant thermoplastic materials have been developed which exhibit significant improvements in toughness over their thermosetting brothers. Compression after impact properties for a specific material are shown on Figure 3 and perhaps this indicates the way ahead for the thermoset pre-impregnators.

Matrix dominated properties are reduced when the glass transition temperature is exceeded. With dry composites this is close to the cure temperature; the latter being typically 175°C with a 190°C post cure for most high performance materials. However, whilst the matrix of all composites absorb moisture to different degrees, the inevitability is that for all the glass transition temperature is reduced. With this comes a reduction in all matrix dominated properties when measured at high temperature. The properties affected are compression and in-plane and interlaminar shear strengths. Whilst as with other properties improvements have been achieved, there appears to be a necessary compromise. For example, improvements in notched compression can be readily effected but at the expense of the previously mentioned compression after impact. This balance clearly needs to be identified by the airframe manufacturer during the material development phase.

The third parameter, briefly mentioned previously, important in the ability of a system to develop the fibre properties, is that of the interface between the fibre and the matrix. This would appear to have had scant attention in the past, primarily because the fibre manufacturer is invariably not the pre-impregnator. Liaison between the two has been poor and this is exacerbated by the geographical separation of the main fibre suppliers, predominantly Japanese, from the impregnator, European or American.

This interface, it is considered by many, holds the key to the improvement of the laminate properties, but it is not merely a matter of increasing the adhesion between the two but one of producing a multi-hatted interface that maximises properties collectively; good adhesion improves some properties at the expense of others.

In an attempt to understand the way ahead for material development, consideration has been given to the various structural properties required of a composite and whether this depends on the fibre, matrix or interface properties. This is shown to the centre and right of Figure 4 and it can be seen that some properties, compression after impact for example, rely on all three facets whilst others are mono-dependent. To the left of this Figure are the improvements to the dependents that are required to effect an increase to the defined structural property. Conflict exists between the requirements and a compromise is difficult to define to maximise all properties. However, it can be considered that the following requirements are dominant :-

- a) A fibre with increased strength and stiffness properties
- b) A fibre with larger diameter
- c) A tougher matrix system
- d) A matrix system less affected by moisture absorption
- e) A fibre-resin combination allowing the fibre to exhibit quasi-plastic behaviour

IMPROVEMENTS			LAMINATE PROPERTIES	FIBRE	MATRIX	INTERFACE
FIBRE	MATRIX	INTERFACE				
HIGHER σ + LIMITED PLASTICITY	LOWER MODULUS + PLASTICITY	POOR ADHESION	NOTCHED TENSION	✓	X	✓
X	HIGHER σ + LIMITED PLASTICITY	GOOD ADHESION	ILSS	X	✓	✓
AS TENSION + HIGHER E + BIGGER DIA	HIGH MODULUS NO PLASTICITY UP TO FIBRE FAILURE	GOOD ADHESION	NOTCHED COMPRESSION	✓	✓	?
AS COMP	DAMAGE SUPPRESSION PLASTICITY HYBRIDISATION	LOW ADHESION	COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT	✓	✓	✓
	STRENGTH AS NOTCHED COMP	GOOD ADHESION				
HIGHER E	HIGHER E	?	MODULUS	✓	X?	X?
HIGHER σ	HIGHER E HIGHER ϵ	POOR ADHESION	UD TENSION	✓	✓	✓

Figure 4. The dependance of laminate properties on composite constituents

The above are considered the improvements required and define the way ahead for the composite material. The ensuing material must compete with the challenge of developing exotic metallic materials.

THE METALLIC CHALLENGE

Perhaps triggered by the inroads composites have made into aircraft structural applications, the metal manufacturers have responded by developing materials with improved specific strengths and industry has contributed to metallic advancement by the development of innovative manufacturing techniques.

Carbon fibre composites are competing primarily with the 2000 and 7000 series aluminium alloys and have, in general, been gaining application. The promise of Aluminium-Lithium Alloys, again a development from the Royal Aircraft Establishment at Farnborough, has, if not stopped, given indications that the forward thrust of composites will decelerate. However, this is but a promise as supply of the high strength, low density material has not yet materialised.

Looking further into the future, metal matrix composites, both titanium and aluminium, raise a challenge that the fibrous non-metallic composites could find difficult to match.

Comparison has been made between a specific property, notched tension strength, for the current generation of composites and metallics along with an indication of the properties anticipated from the developing composite and metallic materials. This information is shown on Figure 5. Whilst these metallic materials are possible they are heavily dependent on development and as such are time dependent. Some indication of the availability of production material for these more advanced metals is given in Figure 6 and it can clearly be seen that a decade is required to ensure availability of some of the more exotic types.

Figure 5. Comparison of specific notched tensile strength for composites and metallics

Figure 6. Timescales for development of materials

Process development has led to the introduction of superplastically formed (SPF) titanium and aluminium components with the titanium banner being carried high by the ability to combine the SPF process with diffusion bonding. Diffusion bonded aluminium alloys has eluded scientists and engineers for many years but the known ability to superplastically form the Aluminium-Lithium alloys has invigorated the search for the solution. With this composites face a mighty challenge.

MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

A situation not unique to composites is the way in which materials are developed. Currently the development driver is a need to compete with alternative materials or new requirements defined by a user. It can be demonstrated that even minor improvements in material performance occur over a period in excess of a project gestation and, as a consequence, the project can utilise only those materials currently available or likely to be available within this period of gestation. For example, significant effort was applied to the development of Aluminium-Lithium alloys commencing some six years ago and the fruits of this are not yet mature. It can therefore be generalised that a decade is not an unrealistic period for the availability of material in a production situation. As would be expected for the necessary development to proceed, visibility of a long term profitable market is required. For some projects this is not necessarily evident by taking either a short or long term view.

This can be demonstrated by the challenging material requirement for HOTOL; a proposed reusable space vehicle exposed to extremes of temperature ranging from 20 to 1700°K. The former being that encountered in the liquid hydrogen tanks and the latter by the kinetic

heating of re-entry. It is quite clear that major material developments will have to take place in a timescale not currently achieved by minor developments. What is the solution?

To date the material suppliers have not tied their development programmes in a contractual sense to the project on which the material will be applied but have, with best intentions, tried to achieve the project requirements. These best intentions in many instances have failed and have caused significant delays or cancellation of the project. It is necessary therefore to formally orchestrate the development involving the suppliers, users and relevant ministries to a common goal; the project. Figure 7 attempts to show the accelerating development required if the challenge of future projects is to be met in a timely manner.

Figure 7. Material development timescales required to meet future projects

THE DESIGN CHALLENGE

The aircraft structural engineers objective is to minimise mass in order to enable the aircraft to maximise performance. Carbon fibre composites offer a material with a specific strength unchallenged across the range of properties by any other single material. It is also well known that of two materials having the same specific stiffness, the one with the lowest density will be the most stable; another driver to the use of C.F.C.

The ability to produce double curvature surfaces and take advantage of the anisotropic behaviour of the material allows the designer a flexibility not available with the more conventional materials. Greater aerodynamic efficiency can be obtained by employing variable

camber, twisted wings with aeroelastic tailoring allowing the wing to perform closer to its aerodynamic optimum at more than one point in the manoeuvre envelope.

These advantages, however, are obtained at a cost during the design phase. With a metallic structure the designer has to produce a structure from an isotropic material, the properties for which are simply expressed as proof and ultimate strengths along with modulus. For composite structures the material has to be designed in parallel with the design of the structure and, as a consequence, the design effort is increased.

Let us first consider the introduction of a new material. One project currently in its infancy is the European multi-national military aircraft project. This is taking advantage of Intermediate Modulus fibres impregnated with a toughened resin system. Work has been undertaken by the suppliers and the partner companies and this identified a limited number of materials deemed worthy of further consideration. This consideration involved the testing of some 2000 specimens to enable the necessary basic data and design carpet plots to be produced. The testing is based on the assumption that the new systems will behave in a similar manner to the current generation, but with improved properties. Will the use of these improved properties, as shown on Figure 5, lead to premature failure by modes not previously encountered? (The ground test programme has been configured to ensure that the risk of this occurring is minimised). With the introduction of every new material will it be necessary to perform such an indepth material evaluation and ensure that the ground test programme is configured to cover all undefinable arisings? If this is the case then changes of material will require careful justification.

Figure 8. Structural clearance based on room temperature testing

Surely the way ahead must be to ensure that the proposed materials can be characterised in such a way that design values can be theoretically generated and that only limited testing will be necessary to confirm the theoretical predictions and ensure that the material variability is within the required limits. However, this is not possible without current knowledge as it is impossible to predict the efficiency of translation of the fibre properties into laminate properties nor to predict the effects of moisture uptake.

Considerable worldwide effort has been applied over the last two decades to satisfy the above requirements and whilst our understanding of composite materials has increased by orders of magnitude the goal remains elusive.

Perhaps, as mentioned previously, the solution lies in establishing more permanent and binding ties between the fibre suppliers, pre-impregnator, user and the relevant ministries (for funding and technical support). A tie up of this nature is currently being arranged within the U.K. between the first three groups on the subject of interface physio-chemistry and its impact on laminate properties.

Armed with a plethora of material data and that from structurally representative elements, the structural engineer can proceed freely with his design; or can he?

Using the wing as an example, a number of fundamental decisions have to be made which are peculiar to composites. Two examples of this are the direction of the 0° fibre orientation and the ply lay-up and stacking sequence over the whole wing. The solution to this could be obtained iteratively by analysing various options and picking that which gives minimum mass whilst achieving the design requirements. This is clearly an inefficient manner in terms of effort and is unlikely to yield the minimum mass.

This problem has been partially resolved by the use of optimisation routines using Finite Element Analysis as the core with integrated post-processors undertaking the detail strength and stability calculations necessary. This yields a notional minimum mass prediction but is it the real minimum?

Following the automated optimisation, which has made significant inroads into the problem, the structure has to be engineered to accommodate requirements which have not been part of the optimisation. This out of necessity adds mass to the structure and inevitably in such a way that the objective of mass minimisation is not achieved.

The aim must therefore be to incorporate into the optimisation more of the detail stressing rules, rules related to the ply lamination and the relationship of stacking sequences in adjacent analysis elements. With this and the automatic generation of aerodynamic loads, consistent with the aeroelastic deformation, the true minimum mass can be achieved. This is clearly a daunting task and one that has never been achieved on metallic structures. However, with the increasing power of F.E.A. techniques, and the associated computers, the drive towards Computer Aided Design and Computer Aided Engineering, the goal is within our reach.

The way ahead is therefore to incorporate within the analysis more of the detail requirements and integrate the C.A.E. system with the C.A.D. system which in turn will link with the C.A.M. network.

Whilst composites have powerful advantages that have allowed them to replace the more traditional materials, the waters are not completely smooth. One area in which composites are disadvantaged is in their ability to produce adequate protection against Electro-magnetic sources and the effects of direct and indirect lightning strike.

Within an aircraft there is a considerable amount of electronic equipment which can be effected adversely by externally generated electro-magnetic signals, either from airborne or ground based sources. A conventional metallic structure bounding the equipment provides internal protection whilst that provided by C.F.C. is deemed unacceptable. A similar situation appertains to Lightning Strike, due to the reduced conductivity of the material. The local ohmic heating in the vicinity of the arc root can be three orders of magnitude greater than in metallic structures resulting in hot spots on the inner surface. In addition, arcing within structures containing fuel can have obvious catastrophic consequences.

Two remedies have to be effected. These are to provide shielding, along with electrical continuity, and structural protection against lightning strike.

The effect of the traditional aluminium structure can be replicated by the addition of a thin foil to the inside of the panel prior to assembly. This, however, is not completely satisfactory as the methods currently adopted have finite life, are prone to damage, and there is some difficulty in producing the necessary electrical continuity through the edge connections. Whilst this latter continuity can be provided by conductive sealants or gaskets it is far from ideal. An alternative to the above is to harden all the electronic equipment and provide the necessary continuity by employing metallic longerons or specific conductivity material.

Protection against lightning strike is aimed at limiting the physical damage to the structure to an acceptable level and preventing local hot spots from being generated; particularly over fuel. The inner foil identified above can adversely affect the situation by attracting the strike to the conducting medium. Hence, in general, an outer surface protection has to be provided. Possible contenders are a metallic mesh integrated into the outer surface of the laminate or plasma sprayed aluminium on the finished component.

Having effected protection of the basic panel, the prevention of arcing inside structure due to the high conductivity of bolts has to be addressed. On current designs this has been achieved by providing a continuous conducting path between fasteners, insulating the bolt heads and oversealing the internal metallic structure. This is not a cost effective system and developments are required to provide a more acceptable solution.

Having designed the aircraft to meet the specification requirements, the two outstanding tasks are to verify by test that the objective has been achieved and secondly to produce the composite structure at minimum mass.

STRUCTURAL TESTING

With conventional metallic structures the route to airworthiness clearance is to undertake tests on critical features, verifying the predicted strain distribution and load carrying capabilities, thereby going a long way to confirming the design at an early stage. This is followed by major static and fatigue tests culminating in the testing of the full vehicle. Almost without exception these are taken to failures in the most critical cases and to ultimate in those not deemed to be critical. Armed with this the structurally cleared manoeuvre envelope can be derived.

Whilst the composite route is not dissimilar there are sufficient significant differences to require a modification to the airworthiness route.

The most critical condition, producing minimum design values, is at high temperature when the laminate has absorbed the relevant amount of moisture. Testing under these conditions on full scale major tests can be prohibitive in terms of cost and timescale and as a consequence alternative routes have to be considered.

The route adopted is to undertake critical feature tests in both the hot/wet and ambient conditions. This allows an understanding to be obtained between the strain distribution from the Finite Element Analysis and that from both test cases. In addition, the relationship between theoretical and actual failing loads is obtained.

Full scale testing is undertaken in the ambient condition up to ultimate load in all cases with the results being correlated to the F.E.A. and the above critical feature tests. Clearance to worst condition is then obtained by interpolating the strains to their limiting value. The logic behind this approach is shown graphically on Figure 8.

Strain measurement is an essential feature of this approach and whilst conventional strain gauges have, and do serve us well in enabling the above clearance route to be effected, improvements in this and methods of failure prediction are required.

Photo-elastic coating is a method that enables strain maps to be produced but the analysis of such data is currently labour intensive and requires post processing to obtain the necessary data.

The panacea to strain measurement would be the ability to cost effectively produce strain contour maps of all the structure, both optically visible and buried within the bowells of the structure. Developments are underway in the area where the structure is optically visible but reliance on strain gauges will still be necessary in hidden areas. These developments are :-

Current developments in fibre optics have achieved, at laboratory level, a degree of success in the measurement of temperature, pressure, displacement, rotation and, to some lesser degree, strain. However, the current state of the art is such that only single point identification is achievable. It is hoped that further development will permit the acquisition of multi-point data from a single fibre optic source, thus permitting the anticipation of a strain contour map via fibre optics. The developments are currently in their infancy and will require significant refinement before they can be used in the test field.

More direct methods of failure prediction have been investigated by many researches and the one showing most promise is Acoustic Emission (A.E.). This is a misnomer as the method relies on the detection of ultrasonic emissions from the structure caused by matrix cracking, fibre failure, joint slip etc.,

The use of A.E. has been accepted in industries where the structural characteristics have been obtained from a series of identical acceptable components, e.g. pressure vessels, and this characteristic has then been used as an inspection acceptance criteria. However, on structures where this characteristic has not been obtained the ability to predict failure to an acceptable tolerance is inadequate to enable realistic clearance to be obtained.

An ability to differentiate between 'clutter' and the more relevant emissions is required and efforts are being directed at characterising the emission signatures of impending failure modes. The way ahead is therefore to improve both the strain measuring capabilities and failure prediction methods.

MANUFACTURING

The largest proportion of the total project cost, excluding end user costs, is in the manufacture of the airframe and the provision and installation of the necessary systems. Whilst reductions in design effort are desirable and strived for they contribute only marginally to the total project cost. Manufacturing costs are of paramount importance and efforts are continually being directed at effecting reductions in this area.

Aerospace industry in general has geared itself over the past decades to machine and manipulate metals in an efficient way consistent with the small batch sizes associated with aircraft production. Numerically controlled machines for metal removal, routing, forming etc., are commonplace throughout the industry and their versatility is being improved by the introduction of flexible manufacturing systems. These systems ensure the optimum availability of part, tool and machine producing a system capable of manufacturing a number of different components with minimal interference to efficiency.

The scene has been set for low cost manufacture of complex metal parts to high tolerances when into the act descends a material requiring a completely new set of skills and equipment from which the structure is to be produced. This material is carbon fibre pre-preg, in the

main, as a continuous tape up to 1.2M wide; an alien material indeed.

Let us consider two aspects of the manufacturing process, detail manufacture and assembly and then examine ways in which both basic and detail design can enable the material to be used in a cost effective manner.

DETAIL MANUFACTURE

The composites known to us all today are primarily thermosetting and due to shop life limitations, have to be stored in freezers at less than -18°C . Having laid up the component they have to be cured and post cured at temperatures up to 200°C in autoclaves and ovens respectively prior to undergoing a non-destructive examination to ensure a defect level consistent with the design requirement. This part of the operation can loosely be related in the metallic field to obtaining a billet from stores, machining the necessary shape under numerical control and performing the required heat treatment and crack detection methods. Figure 9 shows the manufacturing route for a channel section spar manufactured in C.F.C. and Aluminium.

Figure 9. Manufacturing routes for C.F.C. and aluminium channel section spars

At first glance it would appear that the cost of detail manufacture of a composite component is likely to be higher than its metal counterpart and in the main this is the case. The objective therefore is to minimise this cost difference and/or, as will be debated later, reduce the assembly costs to balance this initial difference.

The objective of composite manufacture in the initial part of the process is to lay plies of the appropriate shape on previously laid plies until the drawing requirement has been achieved. Each ply has to be accurately profiled and laid on the mould tool. Let us pause

and examine in detail the ways in which this has been accomplished in the past, the methods adopted today and those required for an efficient way ahead.

These range from highly labour intensive, high cycle time and hence costly processes to those involving highly productive mechanised systems requiring significant capital investment; in some instances in excess of £2 x 10⁶.

These processes can be split into three families :-

- a) Hand lay-up by foil transfer
- b) Hand lay-up using N.C. profiled plies
- c) N.C. tape laying/filament winding

The first of these is an obsolescent process and has in general been superseded by b) and c). However, in the case of extreme double curvature this is very often the only method available to the manufacturer. Foil transfer is a process not dissimilar to domestic dressmaking in which the pattern is laid over the material which is profiled to a given line and then laid on the tool. Cutting is by hand-held knife and clearly the process is labour intensive such that the cost for manufacture by this method can be orders of magnitude greater than that necessary to produce a metal equivalent.

Other industries requiring, as a fundamental operation, the profiling of non-metallic materials are the footwear and rag trade. The profiling of leather for shoes and cloth for suits and dresses are identical to the composite requirement. Out of this relationship rose the broadgood system in which N.C. machines under XY control profile plies to the appropriate shape. The cutting media being either high pressure water, reciprocating knife or laser. The system gaining the largest foothold in aerospace composites is the reciprocating knife, water following behind with virtually no application of laser systems. Whilst the adoption of the broadgoods has made inroads into the part of the process associated with the profiling the necessary labour intensive part of the ply stacking has not been effected.

The next move was therefore to both profile the ply and lay in a parallel operation. This leads obviously to the tape laying concept, the successful implementation of which could theoretically drive the composite manufacturing costs down towards those of metals.

Where are these machines? It is possible that the number of machines in Europe could be counted on the fingers of one hand and, worldwide, it would be difficult to increase this significantly.

Flat bed tape layers are available but have difficulty in achieving the gap/overlap tolerances, ply position and profile shapes required by the designer. Machines having the capability of laying on a double curvature surface are to all intents and purposes non-existent and this is a severe drawback to the reduction in detail manufacturing costs. One obvious difficulty is the need on double curvature surfaces to deviate from the geodesic path if gap/overlap tolerances are to be achieved. This requires a steering system that minimises the fibre perturbations on the inside of the course.

Attempts were made some years ago within the U.K. to provide such a capability and, whilst the development devices demonstrated the feasibility of the method, neither aerospace, the machine tool industry nor the relevant ministry were prepared to fund the fabrication of a production machine. Figure 10 shows the increases in productivity that have been effected by the use of broadgood systems and that which is predicted by the use of an efficient tape laying system.

MANUFACTURING METHOD	RATE OF MATERIAL LAID DOWN (kg/hr)
FOIL TRANSFER METHOD (300mm WIDE TAPE)	0.1 - 0.25
HAND LAY-UP BROADGOODS (1200mm TAPE)	0.7 - 1.25
AUTOMATIC TAPE LAYER	5.0

Figure 10. Manufacturing cost comparisons using hand lay-up, broadgoods and tape laying systems

The way ahead to the advantage of both aerospace and our machine tool industry is to fund the development and manufacture of contour tape layers to satisfy what must be a growing national and international market.

Laminate curing is effected almost universally in autoclaves requiring the controlled application of pressure and temperature to produce a component free from porosity and interlaminar voids. These autoclaves require a large capital investment and are difficult to utilise to maximum efficiency and are costly to operate, requiring an inert atmosphere to minimise the risk of fire.

Autoclave-free curing is a goal that may not be achievable if the composite properties and quality currently enjoyed are to be maintained. Attempts on current epoxy systems to effect vacuum only curing have proved partially successful and this work should be extended to cover the next generation of materials. Consideration should be given to developing systems with this as a fundamental requirement.

A subject not normally directly associated with manufacturing, but an essential part of it is the quality assurance procedures. Composites worldwide have attracted a high level of inspection both of the conventional type and the more sophisticated non-destructive examination. Some 25% of the direct production effort can be

associated with the demonstration of quality.

The procedures normally require the inspector to verify that each ply has been laid in accordance with the design in many instances requiring a one to one relationship between operator and inspector.

By far the greatest cost, however, results from the need, by non-destructive examination, to ensure that the composite component is free from defects that are considered undesirable. This, in the main, requires 100% ultrasonic inspection and, in some instances, is supplemented by 100% radiographic examination.

The need to reduce this punitive requirement is an obvious aim, but it must be tempered by the ultimate goal of ensuring the quality requirements are achieved.

A number of approaches to this problem have been made and the one considered to reap the greatest benefit is that involving the relaxation of the existing requirements. This can be effected by the examination of results from defect investigation programmes and the undertaking of work, where shortfalls occur, to provide additional data. With this, scanning pitches can be increased, components zoned in relationship to the effect of the defect and the introduction of batch acceptance principles become more of a reality.

N.D.E. technique improvement such as increased scanning speeds, multi-probe arrays, alternative techniques and these combined with the above relaxations will result in reductions being made into the N.D.E. support required. The additional consequences of this are the reduction in N.D.E. capital equipment and the reduction in floorspace associated with this activity.

The way ahead is to effect a reduction in inspection support by the relaxation of N.D.E. requirements and the improvement of technique.

ASSEMBLY TECHNIQUES

An assessment of the improvements required in detail manufacture have been addressed above. The cost of assembling these pre-cured items is considered below and it will be demonstrated that cost of assembly is greater than the metal equivalent.

The pre-cured detail in many instances is not moulded to finished size and, as a consequence, requires a machining operation. Conventional HSS cutters are inadequate for this purpose and the more expensive carbide or diamond cutters are required, operating at material removal rates less than for aluminium. These details have then to be assembled and, due to the relatively poor thickness tolerances that can be achieved, shimming, either solid or plastic, is required to fill the resulting gaps. This is invariably a time and cost consuming activity.

Having effected a satisfactory fit between mating parts, fasteners have to be placed which require the preparation of holes, sometimes through different materials, to high tolerances. Again, as with machining, HSS tools are inadequate and must be replaced by carbide

or diamond. Feed rates have to be further reduced to prevent drill break out and again this results in increased assembly costs.

With these increased detail and assembly costs the design advantages identified hitherto may not be realised in the manufacturing area. The solution is obviously to integrate the assembly into the detail by co-bonding/co-curing assemblies or increasing the use of honeycomb sandwich panels.

REDUCING MANUFACTURING COSTS

Before addressing the method of reducing manufacturing costs, let us consider the comparative cost of conventionally fabricated structures in both metal and C.F.C., examining the effects of automation and the reductions in the parts count. The cost information for this assessment has been obtained from Reference 1.

For the purpose of the exercise it has been assumed that the metallic structure will be aluminium and that the material form will be distributed as 30% sheet and 70% machined from billet with a fly to buy ratio of 20%. This results in a cost of 39 units/Kg to procure material and fabricate the details.

Two considerations have been made in the manufacture of composites, one where hand laying-up has been used and the second where the whole of the lay-up is performed by tape layer. Whilst the latter is an objective it is clearly not achievable and a more realistic assessment would be that 70% of the material could be laid by machine. This results in the following detail C.F.C. manufacture costs :-

100% Hand Lay	91 Units/Kg
100% Machine Lay	51 Units/Kg
70% Machine Lay	62 Units/Kg

At best the comparison of these costs with aluminium are disadvantageous to the application of composites.

Assembly costs reflect a similar picture. The metal assembly costs are on average 61 units and the equivalent composite assembly costs are 73 units/Kg. This latter cost assumes the need for shimming over large areas of the structure and the use of attachments requiring close tolerance holes.

Figure 11 graphically illustrates the total cost of manufacture of the two types of structure and clearly indicates that, with a realistic approach to tape lay, composite structures are 32% more expensive than their metallic equivalent, and at worst are 64% more expensive. Clearly, this is an unpalatable situation that has long been realised and steps have been effected that have forced a reversal of the situation.

Figure 11. Comparison of manufacturing costs for conventional metallic and composite structures

Increased automation of the lay-up procedure has already been addressed and the following will address the assembly related aspects.

Compositisation of structures allows the number of part pieces to be reduced either by the introduction of integrally stiffened or honeycomb sandwich panels. It can be shown that the reduction in assembly costs is almost directly proportional to the number of parts and therefore the objective is clear; integrate detail elements into the structure at the part manufacturing stage. This approach is practical only up to certain limits as some structures do not necessarily lend themselves to either of the two remedies discussed above. For example, modern military wings have a low thickness to chord ratio (t/c) and are invariably most structurally efficient when designed as a multi-spar configuration and it could be considered that the traditional methods of assembling details and bolting would have to be used.

Continuing with the use of this example, methods have been developed at British Aerospace in which the substructure has been integrated into the lower wing skin at the detail manufacturing stage. The procedures developed simultaneously cure the substructure and bonds it to the lower skin whilst ensuring an intimate fit between the upper flange and skin. (A release agent is provided between the latter for obvious reasons). Figure 12 shows a schematic of the arrangement.

The advantages of this are :-

- i) Significant reduction of part pieces to assembly
- ii) Less machining of detail parts as spars are edge moulded
- iii) Intimate fit of upper flange to its skin eliminates the need for shim

- iv) Reduced attachment and placement costs
- v) Fuel sealing integrity increased
- vi) Control of aerodynamic shape improved

Figure 12. EAP Spar arrangement

Similar efforts have been directed at fuselage and control surface elements and similar advantages can accrue.

What is the cost advantage of the above? As stated above, the assembly cost is directly proportional to the part piece count and it has been demonstrated that this can be reduced by efficient design and manufacturing techniques to 50% of the metal equivalent. Further cost savings can be effected by the elimination of fasteners due to co-bonding/co-curing and the total effect is to reduce the composite assembly costs to 32 units/Kg. This results, if the figures for the realistic assessment of the proportion of a structure that can be tape laid are used, in a total of 94 units/Kg; a saving of 6% on the metal equivalent. This effect is also shown on Figure 11.

The above has demonstrated that by the innovative application of composites and the development of the appropriate manufacturing techniques the initial cost disadvantage of composites can be overcome. However, it relies on the development of automated tape placement methods or filament winders, and the acceptance of co-bonded/co-cured joints in essential connections between class one structural members.

THE IMPACT OF COMPOSITES

It is now widely accepted worldwide that the application of composites reduces the structural and hence aircraft mass. The application of the first generation composites, using high strength fibres, resulted in mass savings of 12% if the level of compositisation

was 40% and this will probably increase to 15% by the application of Intermediate Modulus fibres and the appropriate tough matrix system. Assuming an aircraft is designed to have a mass of 10,000Kg and have a manoeuvre limit of 10g then the 'nW' is obviously 10^5 . Applying the 15% saving would result in a mass of 8500Kg and hence, based on constant 'nW', the manoeuvre envelope could be increased to almost 12g. If the aircraft is already designed then it may not be possible for other reasons to take advantage of this increase in the envelope.

However, with a project in its infancy, the aircraft could be resized to take advantage of the ability to reduce structural mass resulting in an aircraft some 20% lighter than the basic metallic aircraft. This improved mass saving results from the lighter aircraft potentially having reduced cross-section, hence drag, requiring less fuel to effect the mission, smaller engines to give the same power/weight ratio etc., If this latter option of resizing the engines is taken into account then the aircraft mass could be reduced by a further 4%.

The cost of an aircraft must be in some way proportional to its mass and hence the ability to save mass must result in the production of aircraft at lower cost.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Composites are now part of the fabric of the organisation of all major aircraft manufacturers throughout the world. Their introduction has not been without difficulty and has required the allocation of scarce resource from Corporate and Ministry funds to effect. Whilst the fabric is woven we should not be complacent but strive for allround improvements to take greater advantage of the material's inherent properties.

What avenues should be pursued to achieve this goal? This paper has attempted to identify those considered most necessary and these are summarised below.

Composite Materials

The need exists to further improve composite materials, particularly in the following areas :-

- a) Fibres with increased strength and stiffness
- b) Tougher matrix systems
- c) Matrix systems less affected by moisture
- d) Fibre/resin interface properties

Material Development Strategy

The ad-hoc development of materials, whilst yielding improvements in properties, can be poorly orchestrated and result in individual objectives being satisfied at the expense of a co-ordinated thrust.

The end user must work hand in hand with both the fibre supplier and pre-impregnators to obtain a better understanding of composite behaviour in order that this knowledge can be applied to obtain the desired properties. The users must formulate clear property

goals to enable the suppliers to be correctly directed.

The above development activities and user goals must be positively co-ordinated and binding to produce results against managed programmes.

Structural Design

Two areas have been highlighted here where the way ahead will be smoothed if achieved. The first is the development of an ability to characterise composite materials based on element properties in order that the mechanical properties subsequently required can be determined theoretically. The current practice of producing data sheets from a combination of empirical and theoretical information will be much simplified, costing less and enable alternative materials to be considered and more rapidly introduced.

Improvements in optimisation techniques, with the introduction of more of the detail strength requirements and the automatic generation of aerodynamic loads, is seen as the second requirement.

Structural Testing

The airworthiness route relies heavily on the successful completion of a structural test programme in which, due to variability and temperature/moisture effects, metallic parts fail prior to the composite. In order to predict the composite failure it is necessary to extrapolate from strain readings and it is in this area that techniques for low cost/rapid measurement, preferably producing contour maps, are developed.

Failure prediction, perhaps by the development of acoustic emission techniques, should be improved.

Manufacturing

The manufacturing costs of detail parts is prohibitive with hand lay-up techniques and the development and introduction of machines capable of laying on double curvature surfaces is seen as a high priority. Despite considerable effort over the last decade this has not been achieved. The effort required to support the N.D.E. of composite parts is of the order of 25% of the direct workforce. Improvement in techniques and the introduction, wherever possible, of more relaxed standards are clearly an avenue for reducing cost.

Finally, the development of production techniques which integrate parts in the detail manufacturing stage will reduce the parts count and reduce total manufacturing cost.

The failure of composites is secure for the foreseeable future but the threat of advanced metallics should not be ignored. The inherent advantages of composites should be developed in all avenues to ensure their appropriate contribution to the future of the Aerospace Industry.

REFERENCES

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